

DESCRIPTION OF PHILOSOPHICAL TERMS OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE ACCORDING TO THEIR STRUCTURE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7468816>

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Abstract: This article provides an overview of encyclopedic dictionaries and explains some scientific and philosophical terms, concepts, currents, directions, theories, doctrines used in social-political and scientific-popular literature and widely used in spiritual life. Units with certain terminological characteristics are semantically divided into hierarchical groups. When creating a database of philosophical terms in the language corpus, taking into account their characteristics, the methods of their semantic tagging are explained

Keywords: attribute, philosophy, classification, vocabulary, term

Received: 20-12-2022

Accepted: 21-12-2022

Published: 22-12-2022

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When terms are studied and analyzed from a linguistic point of view, their form-structural features are also studied. Through the form-structural classification of terms, it is possible to come to theoretical conclusions about their formation, formation and semantic composition.

In most of the studies conducted on Uzbek terminology, the structural analysis of field terms was carried out, and the terms *compound*, *pair*, *complex*, *composition*, *compound*, *combination* were used for units consisting of more than one stem.

R. Doniyorov considers terms consisting of more than one lexical element as syntactically formed terms. According to the scientist, in the technical terminology of the Uzbek language, compared to single-word terms, syntactically formed terms occupy an important place. The reason for this is that the terms formed by the syntactic method are considered an important nominative source in the Uzbek language, as in all languages. [1 : 148]

Researcher M. Ahatova studies lexemes related to woodworking and explains on the basis of examples that such terms are formed by purely semantic, semantic-syntactic methods. He notes that woodworking compound terms are formed as noun+noun and adjective+noun [2:24] .

N. Qasimov divided scientific and technical terms with more than one component into such types as joint, double and hybrid ¹⁴⁹. [3:47]

¹⁴⁹Kasimov N. Issues of scientific and technical terminology of the Uzbek language (issues of word acquisition and affixation). - Tashkent: Science, 1985. - B. 47.

In T. Valiev's dissertation entitled "Structural-semantic features and lexicographic interpretation of Uzbek language road construction terms", road construction terms are structurally divided into the following groups: 1) simple terms; 2) joint terms; 3) double terms; 4) compound terms; 5) Abbreviated terms ¹⁵⁰. [4:55]

E. Sobirova recommends that in researching the structural features of legal terms, they should be divided into the following groups: 1) simple; 2) joint; 3) couple; 4) compound ¹⁵¹. [5:45] _ _

Uzbek terminological system , the simple terms related to philosophy can be divided into the following two groups according to their composition: simple basic terms; simple artificial word form terms.

In the 5-volume explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the following can be included in simple basic terms: *attribute, basis, survival, time, unity, time, conflict, perception, illusion, category, content, space, matter, quantity, relationship, relative, object, consciousness, spirit , reason, quality, scholastic, chance, life, law, action, truth*

If you pay attention, there are lexemes that bring the functional forms of the verb in the basic philosophical terms. For example, *jump, save* . These lexemes have acquired a philosophical terminological character:

JUMP 1 Jump fl. each n. *Jump on one leg. He leapt over the wall and rushed forward as hard as he could.* S. Anorboev, Aksoy. **2** Independent training in a specific sport. *Skydiving. High jump. Long jump.* **3 fls.** The process of transition of quantitative changes to qualitative changes ¹⁵². [6:45]

It is clear from the available comments that this lexeme in the form of *c akra+sh* with the last meaning (the process of transition of quantitative changes to qualitative changes) expressed a terminological meaning.

SAVE 1 Save fl. each n. *Law of conservation of matter (fls).* **2** Self-defense; protection, protection. *Protection from the effects of atomic radiation. Fire prevention rules. A person should be protected from various harmful diseases and infectious diseases. From the newspaper* ¹⁵³.

This lexeme is evaluated as a philosophical term with the meaning of the law of conservation of matter in the form of mind +work .

¹⁵⁰Valiev T.Q. Structural-semantic features and lexicographical interpretation of Uzbek language road construction terms: Philol. science. false on dr. ... diss. - Samarkand, 2018. - B. 55.

¹⁵¹Sobirova E. Giving legal terms in the "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language": Doctor of Philology (PhD) diss... - Tashkent, 2022. - 179 p. - B. 45.

¹⁵²An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. 5 volumes. - Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2006. Volume 3. - 688 p. - B. 456.

¹⁵³An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. 5 volumes. - Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2006. Volume 3. - 688 p. - B. 500.

Philosophical simple artificial terms occupy an important place in OTIL. Such terms are formed by the morphological method. Simple pseudo-philosophical terms are formed using the following affixes:

1) **-anti:** *antithesis*

ANTITHESIS fls , *mnt.* A judgment, discussion, opinion against the thesis; opposite thesis ¹⁵⁴.

2) **-lamchi:** *primary, secondary*

1 s.t. First. *We will reunite him with the one who loves him. This is my primary condition!* K. Yashin, Hamza. **2** The first place in the process of an event: main, first. *Matter is primary (fls). In words related to the noun group, the lexeme is in the primary speech base position. "EXCESS". Primary cosmic rays use up their energy very quickly as they pass through the Earth's atmosphere. From the newspaper* ¹⁵⁵.

3) **-lik (-liq):** *existence, beauty, absence, specificity*

1 fls . An objective world, universe, existence beyond human consciousness and intuition. *Ahmad went outside. The day was hot, everything was burning brightly.* F. Musajonov, Him mat. ... *both the desert and the whole existence seem to be sleeping. "Guards of Uzbekistan". The desire is to perfect the existence of man, surprisingly, man is not perfected by existence.* E. Vahidov, Love.

2 A person's body, body, posture. *I am your wife, Otabek, as my being is connected with the flame of your love.* A. Qadiri, Past days. *Pain consumed his entire being. "Youth". I saw a girl sitting by the river and singing with all her heart. "Star of the East". A cold sweat broke out from his being.* H. Tokhtaboev, The land of sweet melons.

3 All, all, whole. *The Uzbek mother was furious at her son's "kicking over the dead" and poured out her fury on her husband.* A. Qadiri , Past Days ¹⁵⁶.376

4) **-ism:** *idealism, materialism, objectivism, sensualism*

MATERIALISM [*fr.* material - mod-diy] **1 fls.** Contrary to idealism, it is a philosophical direction based on emphasizing the primacy of matter, objective existence, its existence independent of human will, spirit, and consciousness, and the duality of spirit, consciousness, and the ability to know objective existence and its laws.

2 s. t. Approaching existence and life from a real, material point of view ¹⁵⁷.

5) **ir-:** *irrational*

¹⁵⁴An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. 5 volumes. - Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2006. Volume 1. - 680 p. - B. 103.

¹⁵⁵An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. 5 volumes. - Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2006. Volume 1. - 680 p. - B. 330.

¹⁵⁶An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. 5 volumes. - Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2006. Volume 1. - 680 p. - B. 376.

¹⁵⁷An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. 5 volumes. - Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2006. Volume 2. - 671 p. - B. 650.

IRRATIONAL [*lat.* irrationalis - unreasonable; done without thought] **1 fls.** Unlawful and therefore unintelligible, knowable and logically explainable; out of mind. *Irrational view.*

2 mat. Cannot be measured, expressed, or calculated by a whole number; which requires, in addition to the arithmetic operation, the operation of finding roots. *Irrational equation. Irrational numbers* ¹⁵⁸.

6) **-ist: materialist**

MATERIALIST 1 fls. A supporter of materialism, a person who follows the path of materialism. *As much of a materialist as I am, I like to believe that the state of inspiration is magical.* U. Normatov, Talent education ¹⁵⁹.

7) **-iv: objective, subjective**

II 1 fls . Outside of consciousness and not directly related to consciousness. *Objective law of nature. Objective existence (reality).*

2 Free from error or subjective opinion; unbiased, unbiased, unbiased. *Objective assessment, Objective conclusion. To approach the issue objectively. Since we received a complaint, we must look at this fact objectively! "Youth"* ¹⁶⁰.

8) **-ism: rationalism, realism, relativism, subjectivism**

RATIONALISM [*fr.* rationalism < *lat.* rational - based on reason, intelligence] *fls.* A philosophical direction that considers the mind as the main, decisive source of true knowledge ¹⁶¹.

The term subjectivism contains two word-forming affixes. The subject is the base, i.e. the leading morpheme, -iv and -ism are affixes. The basis for making this term is *subjective*. Therefore, the last suffix was taken into account in this word.

SUBJECTIVISM 1 ayn. subjective idealism q. subjective.

2 fl. An idealistic doctrine that explains the existence and change of things and events not on the basis of laws, but on the activity of the subject.

3 Subjective view, one-sided approach to the issue from the point of view of one's personal opinion and judgments. *In the interpretation of life events , the author's warm "subjectivism" is nourished by lyrical, emotional elements. "EXTREME"* ¹⁶².

9) **-iy : causal**

CAUSAL [due to reason] *fls.* Causal; because of *Causal connection* ¹⁶³.

10) **-iyat: causation**

¹⁵⁸An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. 5 volumes. - Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2006. Volume 2. - 671 p. - B. 263.

¹⁵⁹An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. 5 volumes. - Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2006. Volume 2. - 671 p. - B. 650.

¹⁶⁰An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. 5 volumes. - Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2006. Volume 3. - 688 p. - B. 384.

¹⁶¹An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. 5 volumes. - Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2006. Volume 3. - 688 p. - B. 81.

¹⁶²An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. 5 volumes. - Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2006. Volume 3. - 688 p. - B. 619.

¹⁶³An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. 5 volumes. - Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2006. Volume 3. - 688 p. - B. 437.

CAUSATION [connection, connection] *fls.* A category that indicates the natural, social, objective interaction and connection of events. *The law of causality* ¹⁶⁴.

11) - ika: sophistry

SOPHISTICS [*Greek.* *sophistike* - the skill of deviously leading a discussion, changing its direction] *fls.* Deliberately breaking the laws of logic and arguing based on false arguments ¹⁶⁵.

hybrid terms as a form of compound terms . In his opinion, "hybrid terms are new types of combined terms that appeared in Uzbek scientific and technical terminology in recent years. The word " *hybrid* " in a broad sense means "hybrid" words made up of different language elements. For example, the term " *quasiparticles* " in physics is a hybrid word, it is formed by combining the Latin word form " *quasi* " (false, false) and the Uzbek word " *particle* " ¹⁶⁶.

According to T. Valiev, all the second components of these hybrid terms are certainly not Uzbek words. For example, words such as *industry, photograph, and particle* are native layer units. There are also a lot of hybrid terms in the road construction terminology consisting of Uzbek words . For example, *road construction, traffic, car accident , etc.*¹⁶⁷

Among the philosophical terms, there are hybrid terms, both of which do not belong to the Uzbek language. Including:

PANTHEISM [pan.. + Yun . *theos* - god] *religion. fls.* A religious-philosophical doctrine that considers that God is one thing with nature, that they form a whole. *Pantheism and deism were the most important forms of advancing philosophical ideas in the medieval context.* "Gulistan" ¹⁶⁸.

EMPIRIOCRTISM [*Greek.* *empei ria* – experience + *kritique* (*techne*) – the art of critical discussion] *fls.* A *subjective-idealist movement* in philosophy that appeared at the end of the **19TH** century, denying the objectivity of the material world, and viewing matter as a product of consciousness ¹⁶⁹.

It seems that these terms are composed of two components and belong to the mastery layer.

From the above, it can be concluded that the philosophical terminology of the Uzbek language has its place in the language system as a separate microsystem. They mostly have a simple structure. Simple root and simple artificial terms are

¹⁶⁴An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. 5 volumes. - Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2006. Volume 3. - 688 p. - B. 437.

¹⁶⁵An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. 5 volumes. - Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2006. Volume 3. - 688 p. - B. 597.

¹⁶⁶Kasimov N. Issues of scientific and technical terminology of the Uzbek language (issues of word acquisition and affixation). - Tashkent: Science, 1985. - B. 47.

¹⁶⁷Valiev T.Q. Structural-semantic features and lexicographical interpretation of Uzbek language road construction terms: Philol. science. false on dr. ... diss. - Samarkand, 2018. - B. 53.

¹⁶⁸An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. 5 volumes. - Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2006. Volume 2. - 671 p. - B. 229.

¹⁶⁹An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. 5 volumes. - Tashkent: "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" State Scientific Publishing House, 2006. Volume 5. - B. 38.

important. Although less numerous, there are also hybrid terms. During the research, there were no double, complex, content, compound terms at all. Most of these philosophical terms are related to belonging to the mastery layer.

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